

The digital language vitality scale: a model for assessing digital vitality of languages

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Abstract

This document is currently an ongoing documentation of the work about the Digital Language Vitality Scale and related indicators. It is meant to feed two kinds of results: a document explaining the DLVS for use in Digital Language Planning and a research (journal) paper describing 1) a digital language vitality scale with ideal, measurable indicators; 2) pragmatic considerations on measurability and suggestions on how to estimate indicators; 3) a test case on the 4 languages of the project.

1 Introduction

Language is a primary vector for communicating information and knowledge, thus the opportunity to use one's language on the Internet will determine the extent to which one can participate in emerging knowledge societies.

UNESCO

There are more than 7000 languages spoken on our planet today¹, but only a dozen or so are flourishing in the digital medium with advanced services and communication technologies. In a hyper-connected and increasingly digital world, the ability to use the Internet and Information and Communications Technologies (ICTs) in the language you speak determines one's inclusion or exclusion from the Knowledge Society. Limitations in the multilingual skills of computers and mobile devices widen the digital gap, which excludes hundreds of millions of people from accessing the full benefits of the Internet and digital

¹7099 according to the Ethnologue as of September, 2017. This figure is constantly in flux. See <https://www.ethnologue.com/guides/how-many-languages>

technologies. For example, only a tiny fraction of the world's languages is currently being used on Twitter and Facebook. According to W3Techs statistics,² the 87,2% of websites are in one among 10 languages only, and 38 languages account for 94,8% of web site content. Among the languages used by 0,1% of the websites are not only relatively small languages like Estonian and Latvian, but also languages spoken by millions of people, like Hindi (260 million speakers, according to the Ethnologue), Thai (20.5 million), or Indonesian (198 million). Therefore, despite the fact that a language may be flourishingly spoken, its digital vitality may not parallel its non-digital one. In some areas of the world, the infrastructure for connectivity is limited or too expensive for the average person. Using the Internet requires reading and writing skills, but much of the world's population remains non-literate in their mother tongue, their regional language of wider communication or both. Using the Internet presupposes basic proficiency with computers or other digital devices. Many people do not have the resources to gain these skills, though smartphones are bridging this gap in many parts of the world. Many of the world's languages still lack a writing system. Others may have established writing systems, but there are no fonts or keyboards available for using the language on digital platforms. Writing software for these scripts requires special engineering skills.

The assessment of current gaps, needs and requirements regarding the extent to which a language community can use its language on digital media and devices is a useful exercise, in particular in the framework of *digital language planning*. The purpose of this document is to describe a tool for assessing the degree of vitality of a language, the Digital Language Vitality Scale and its associated indicators. The Digital Language Vitality Scale (DLVS) is intended as an instrument for language communities to assess the level of digital vitality of their language and help them plan ahead the measures they wish to take in order to increase the digital use of their language. Observation, assessment, planning and uptake of measures are the four steps identified by the Digital Language Diversity project³ and offered to any language community wishing to steer the digital development of their language. The current digital vitality status of a language will serve as a baseline for making informed decisions regarding its digital development. The particular types of actions and measures needed will be chosen by the language community, and in this respect the DLDP project wishes to act as an external consultant providing guidance and expertise about the range of possible actions to be taken. These actions are detailed in the DLDP *Digital Language Survival Kits*, one for each of the *digital vitality levels* identified by the DLVS. Therefore, the DLVS is the first but necessary step in digital language planning, a process — we stress it once again — that must be community-based and rooted in the community's vision of what is desirable and achievable.

²https://w3techs.com/technologies/overview/content_language/all

³Henceforth DLDP: <http://www.dldp.eu>

2 Digital Language Vitality

Digital Language Vitality is here defined as the extent to which a language is usable, present, and actually used over the Internet and digital devices (PCs as well as mobile phones, smartphones, tablets, game consoles, Internet TV, etc.).

The exercise of measuring the digital vitality of a language nowadays can be restricted to the observation of a language to a particular domain: the (online) digital one.

Measurement avails itself of two instruments: a scale and a set of indicators. In developing them, the main challenge is twofold: a) to develop a model that is *sufficiently expressive* and b) to devise *reliable* and possibly *measurable* quantitative and qualitative indicators for measuring the degree of language vitality of a language. Another challenge we are aware of is the need of indicating possible sources for the data feeding the indicators.

The topic of Digital Language Vitality is a relatively new area of study and research. In 2012, the META-NET “Language White Papers” ([24]) introduced the concept of *digital extinction* to refer to the risk faced by the majority of EU official languages of a dramatic contraction of uses as a result of the lack of technological support. The most influential work related to the topic of Digital Language Vitality is the article by András Kornai ([20]), who in his paper “Digital Language Death” proposes four levels of digital vitality, elaborated by “bringing the traditional methods of language vitality assessment to the digital realm” [21, 1]:

1. Still: there is no observed use of the language; the language is no longer capable of digital ascent.
2. Heritage: there are language materials, but these are “languages that are digitally archived”
3. Vital: languages that do not have such support, but are still “used for communication by native speakers”
4. Thriving: large use by both native and foreign speakers; extensive computer support

This classification has been revised and extended by Gibson ([15]), in order to more properly take into account social and community digital micro-uses of the language (e.g. by texting or messaging) that represent incipient digital presence. Gibson introduces two new categories between *Heritage* and *Still*: the ‘Emergent’ category tries to capture incipient dynamic uses of a language, and the ‘Latent’ one serves for classifying languages potentially able to develop digitally, but for which no digital use is observed at the time of the inquiry. The last category of Kornai’s categories (Still) appears to be slightly reformulated as well:

1. Still: the language shows no sign of digital ascent, which appears unlikely.

2. Latent: the language shows no sign of digital ascent, but their digital use is possible⁴
3. Emergent: the language shows community use of texting and social media messaging
4. Heritage: there are language materials, but these are “languages that are digitally archived”
5. Vital: languages that do not have such support, but are still “used for communication by native speakers”
6. Thriving: large use by both native and foreign speakers; extensive computer support

3 The DLDP Scale for Digital Language Vitality

Building upon previous work by Kornai and Gibson, the Digital Language Vitality Scale proposed here is articulated on six levels, which are informally described below⁵:

1. Pre-digital (**P**). The language is not present on (online) digital media and it lacks the basic infrastructure for digital use. It has no technological support; the infrastructure for connectivity is limited or too expensive for the average person, therefore the language cannot expand on the Internet; people’s digital proficiency is non-existent or very low.
2. Dormant (**D/S**).Some of the main preconditions for digital usage of a language are in place: e.g. connectivity is ensured, there is some degree of Internet penetration and most language speakers are at least basically digitally literate. However, there is no technological support for the use of the language (e.g. there is no keyboard support for writing the language, no t9, auto-correction, etc.), especially online. Therefore, although speakers are in principle capable of using the language digitally, in practice they do not do so because the language still needs some basic technological development to make it possible.
3. Emergent (**E**). Internet penetration is good, speakers are digitally literate. Overall, however the language still enjoys limited technological support (e.g. such as fonts and keyboards), although some basic language resources (one e-dictionary, a small corpus) might be available. Texting and messaging as well as social media start to be used in the language, albeit not yet extensively. Wikipedia, if present, is smaller than 10.000 articles, and a couple of digital media might be available .

⁴For a list of the conditions under which digital use is considered possible, see [15, 65].

⁵Quantitative issues should become clearer in section X where we discuss the relevant dimensions individually and offer for each dimension a mapping to these levels.

4. Developing (**De**). The language shows some usage over communication and social media, although frequency may still be occasional. Some digital media and services may be available, as well as a medium-sized Wikipedia; basic language resources are in place, and there might be evidence of more advanced ones. At least one among the social media and the operating systems used by the speakers' community might be localised. An online machine translation service or tool might be available, for one language pair at least.
5. Vital (**V**). The language is used regularly for e-communication and on social media, some of which may have a localised interface. There is a considerable variety of digital media available. Language resources are widely available. Wikipedia projects are big and actively used. The language can be used in all digital domains. Most used operating systems and general purpose software localised in the language. There is evidence of machine translation tools/services.
6. Thriving (**T**). The language is used extensively and without any technological barriers in all current digital domains, from communicative to transactional ones. The latest technology is available.

Each level presupposes and builds on top of the previous one.

Since the concept of Digital Language Vitality is closely tied to the existence of a living language community, the scale does not provide a level corresponding to Kornai's and Gibson's category "Heritage", which was intended to capture the case of languages that are no longer spoken but are indeed present on digital media under the form of digital archives. As such, the Heritage level does not imply the existence of a living language community, which is a prerequisite for digital use of languages.⁶

4 Digital Language Vitality Indicators

How do we measure Digital Language Vitality, and attribute a particular level to living languages? What are the factors that need to be taken into account to assess it?

It must be borne in mind that reliable indicators of the vitality of a digital language, i.e. of the extent to which a language is digitally prosperous by increasing its presence and use online, are unfortunately still missing.

The first attempt in this respect was made by Kornai ([20]), who devises a set of indicators modelled after those developed for ethnolinguistic vitality assessment (Graded Intergenerational Disruption Scale or GIDS [13] and Extended Graded Intergenerational Disruption Scale or EGIDS [22]). In doing so,

⁶Exactly like conservationist biologists are interested in living plants and species, a measurement of Digital Language Diversity needs to focus on vital languages, not dead ones. Yet the web can host heritage languages, such as corpora of Ancient Greek or Old Saxon poems, or material in and about planned languages that are no longer in use, such as Volapük.

he correctly identifies active digital uses of a language as the crucial factor in determining its Digital Vitality, and suggests complementing the indicators of digital presence of a language (e.g. the number of web pages in a given language) with other proxies for digital language use, such as the existence of an active Wikipedia community in the language.

In our opinion, it is important both to stress the incipient digital uses of a language (a point already made by Gibson, see [15]) and its technological support, as well as to distinguish between communicative digital uses of a language (i.e. the language is digitally used for communication purposes mainly) and *transactional* ones (i.e. the ability to perform actions such as buying, making reservations, etc. using a given language, “what you can do” digitally with the language), the latter presupposing a level of technological advancement much higher than the former. Moreover, the availability of language technologies supporting the digital use of a language is another important indicator to be taken into account. Furthermore, since the applicability and usability of a scale very much depends on the availability of reliable and measurable indicators, it appears that Kornai’s indicators listed above are too shallow as categories, for which it is very difficult to associate a reliable proxy:

1. size of the digitally enabled population: size of digital natives’ population
2. digital prestige
3. identity function
4. functional domains (range of digital use)
 - (a) some kind of *locale* or *internationalization* (often abbreviated as ‘i18n’) support that enables the input (writing) and output (reading) of native characters; the availability of an input method
 - (b) a variety of word-level tools such as dictionaries, stemmers, and spellcheckers
 - (c) phrase- and sentence-level tools (that can only be built on some pre-existing character- and word-level standard), such as part-of-speech taggers, named entity recognizers, chunkers, speech recognition, and machine translation.
5. presence of Wikipedia

With the exception of categories 4 and 5, the other categories can hardly be coupled with quantifiable indicators. Therefore, it seems more appropriate to treat them as meta-categories, or cluster labels.

There are many different possible reasons why a language is absent or with little presence on the digital domain. A language can be digitally absent either because the technical infrastructure is lacking, or because it is not used even if it would be possible in principle. The Internet is not immune to social aspects of dominance, and it tends to maintain the imbalance between majority and minority languages that is found in the real world. Therefore, a language could

Indicator	
1. Evidence of connectivity	
2. Digital literacy	
3. Internet penetration or digital population size ⁷	<i>digital capacity</i>
4. Character/script encoding	
5. Availability of language resources	
<hr/>	
6. Use for e-communication	
7. Use on social media	<i>digital presence and use</i>
8. Availability of Internet media	
9. Wikipedia size	
<hr/>	
10. Available Internet services	
11. Localised social networks	
12. Localised software	<i>digital performance</i>
13. Machine translation tools/services	
15. Dedicated Internet top-level domain	

Table 1: Digital Language Vitality Indicators

be not used for lack of institutional support, or for a submissive attitude of their speakers. These are very different situations that need to be distinguished in a vitality scale, as they require different actions of intervention, and presuppose totally different background situations. In our proposed framework, we distinguish among three groups of indicators: a group pertaining to a language *digital capacity*, a group related to a language *digital presence and use*, and a group related to a language *digital performance*. From the interplay of these axes we can derive a picture of the extent to which a language is able to perform in the digital domain.

As a preliminary extension to Kornai’s and others’ previous work, we propose the following list of indicators for assessing Digital Language Vitality.

The horizontal lines highlight a clustering of indicators into groups describing different dimensions of digital use. The first five indicators globally assess the *digital usability* of a language, from the very basic conditions of having a connection and being able to operate a digital device to the possibility for a language to be written using standardized characters and the availability of basic language resources, which in turn determine the extent to which some language-based applications can be developed (which, in turn, will have again an effect on language digital usability). Indicators from 6 to 9 refer to levels of *digital language use*, in an ascending degree of complexity as well as of identity function. Finally, indicators from 10 to 15, while still focusing on actual use of a language, introduce a dimension of performance and *digital prestige*: when some digital

services such as e-booking, e-commerce, or information searches are localised in a language, it means that the digital content available in a given language is already well established. Speakers have the desire to use these services in their own language, which can or cannot be enabled, but nevertheless the service is offered in the language. The last two indicators additionally can be considered as proxies for a) an advanced level of development of language technology and b) a strong digital identity.

4.1 Digital Capacity

By “digital capacity” we mean the extent to which a language is infrastructurally and technologically supported and may function in the digital world. Basic conditions such as availability of an Internet connection and digital literacy must be met for a community to use a language digitally. Similarly, the availability of functionalities such as spell checkers over mobile phones can boost — in principle — its use by making its typing easier and faster. A language’s digital capacity only refers to its potential to be used digitally, but it is by no means a guarantee that a community will use it. This is the case, for instance, of many European regional or minority languages: although most of these languages meet all the requirements of digital capacity, they are often little used in comparison to the national language of the countries where they are spoken. Other factors (psychological submission, lack of competence in the written language, lack of available digital spaces — forums, blogs — where the language is used) can determine a poor digital use.

4.1.1 Evidence of connectivity

Internet connectivity is the ability of the members of a community to connect to the Internet, be it from a fixed or mobile broadband. Information and Communication Technology, and the Internet in particular, has been one of the main factors of societal changes in the last few decades. (see Eurostat Digital Society Statistics). Because it enables people to access information and services at any time and from any place, Internet in particular, has become of vital importance for daily life in all aspect of society, from education to work and even leisure (see Deloitte <find better citation way> for various benefits of Internet). Good, pervasive connectivity is therefore a fundamental prerequisite not only for closing the so-called digital divide, but it has a big impact in the vitality potential of languages as well. Even in the well connected, digitally advanced, Europe, however connectivity is not equally distributed across territory or social strata (sources?), and this has an obvious impact on the digital presence especially of regional and minority languages. Policy makers world wide nowadays highlight the strategic importance of promoting better on-line access to all citizens, not only to foster economic growth but also inclusiveness and participation. Although the linguistic factor is still largely underestimated, there is wide recognition today of the fact that connectivity is a transversal issue that impacts digital development as a whole. Certainly, connectivity alone is no

Label	Score	Micro Indicators
no or scarce	1	scarce BB or 3G internet access
good	2	good BB or 3G internet access

Table 2: Evidence of connectivity

guarantee of digital uptake, nor of digital vitality of languages, nevertheless its foundational importance cannot be denied in any assessment involving ICT. The European Commission indeed includes connectivity as a relevant dimension for the calculation of the Digital Economy Society Index (DESI) and identifies four factors that equally impact on the development of an inclusive digital society: fixed broadband, mobile broadband, speed and affordability [2, pp.7-8].

In the assessment of the digital vitality of languages that we propose here, the connectivity dimension is considered as a minimal requirement and should ideally reflect the level of broadband connectivity, including mobile connectivity, within the particular community of speakers of the language under assessment⁸. As such it should map on the lowest levels of the scale, as positive evidence of connectivity does not tell us much about the actual presence of a given language on-line. In fact, while the absence of connectivity among the target language community must imply that the language has no significant digital use, evidence of good and widespread connectivity does not necessarily imply active digital use of the language, which therefore can be classified minimally at the dormant level. Following the EC indications, we consider as indicative factors for a potential active use of a language online the availability of broadband access from home or of at least 3G on mobile devices (synthetically presented as BB in table 2 below.

How to estimate connectivity. Ideally, one would need official statistics on Internet connectivity among the community of speakers of the language under assessment. In practice, such information is still non-existent for many languages, and for regional or minority languages in particular⁹. To date, you might want to use data about Internet connection in the region or country where the language is spoken, keeping in mind that these are rough and potentially incorrect approximations. At the time of writing, for European languages, the Eurostat statistics for Digital Economy and Society are useful sources of information: Eurostat offers data both at country level [11] and per NUTS2 regions (Nomenclature of Units for Territorial Statistics) [10]¹⁰. The regional statis-

⁸The situation might in fact differ considerably from connectivity at country level

⁹We recommend national and international statistics institutions to include the language dimensions in their periodic surveys, as this might considerably help minority (language) communities.

¹⁰The International Telecommunication Union (ITU) also provides reliable internet statistics at world level; breakdowns however are available only per country (<https://www.itu>).

tics, although do not taking into account the linguistic context, may be more accurate than statistics at national level. In fact, Internet connection might be influenced by socio-economic factors that affect only a part of the country (where the minority language is spoken). In certain cases it might be possible to get more specific statistics if the demographic details of the minority community are known. For example, the site <http://www.stat.fi> offers statistics on Internet usage in Finland based on age, place of residence and other features. We therefore suggest you to verify first whether more detailed statistics are available for your country / region / language from local reliable sources.

As reference value for setting the discriminating threshold we might take the minimum of a set of relevant countries or regions, for instance of the countries whose main/official language is among the top 10 most used languages on the Internet. In the specific case of European languages we might set the threshold at the minimum figure reported by Eurostat among: UK, Spain, Portugal, France and Germany (e.g. 76%). Practically, this would mean to assign score 1 for Broadband access < 76% and score 2 otherwise.

4.1.2 Digital literacy

Digital literacy refers to the skills required to achieve digital competence, i.e. the confident and critical use of information and communication technology (ICT) for work, leisure, learning and communication¹¹ Digital literacy is another essential precondition (i.e. an enabling factor) for digital language vitality. If speakers of the language are digitally not (or very minimally) proficient, then it becomes evident that their native language has little chance of being digitally lively, notwithstanding its spoken vitality or technological readiness. In the present study, ‘digital competence’ is one of the dimensions that shall be considered for assessing the potential for digital presence/vitality of languages. As such it should address the digital skills that members of a given language-speaking community possess, irrespective of the language(s) they use on digital media and devices. The rationale behind this being that, if a person has high digital skills, she/he is (potentially) able to use her/his own mother tongue digitally. Whether a given language is or is not actually used digitally is another matter, whose reasons shall be searched for elsewhere.

So, what is ‘digital competence’? There is a vast literature on digital literacy and research is ongoing. In fact, the very notion of digital literacy naturally changes/evolves in time, as technology progresses at rapid pace and the skills needed for using such technology in the digital world increase both in number and in complexity. A full account of the debate around digital literacy research, however interesting, is beyond the scope of the present paper. The interested reader might refer to [3], [17] and [7] (to mention just a few of the most recent works).

For the purposes of the present study, we make reference to the European

int/en/ITU-D/Statistics/Pages/stat/treemap.aspx

¹¹source: Eurostat Glossary.

Digital Competence Framework for citizens (DigComp)¹², a framework designed and adopted by the European Commission for the (self-)evaluation and improvement of citizens’ digital skills/competences [12], which provides a common reference for digital competence in Europe. Because it is the result of extensive comparative and collaborative research on digital literacy assessment, it is well grounded, solid and sufficiently general to be safely adopted for the assessment of the digital vitality of languages.

DigComp defines 21 digital skills organised into 5 competence areas, or domains, and proficiency levels (3 in the first 2013 version, DigComp 1.0; 8 in its latest 2017 version, DigComp2.1 [26][5]). The framework is supported by the ECDL foundation, which has recently mapped its programme to the DigComp skills; is adopted by the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI)¹³ to create a set of indicators for assessing Digital Skills¹⁴. Moreover, on the basis of these competences Eurostat developed specific indicators and related questions for its annual ICT survey on ICT usage¹⁵.

The areas identified are briefly reported below, with the first three clearly more relevant for our case (see [5] for details on the skills defined for each area):

- Area 1. **Information** and data literacy: people can articulate information needs, locate and retrieve digital data, information and content, judge the relevance of the source, store, manage, and organise digital data, information and content;
- Area 2. **Communication** and collaboration: people do interact, communicate and collaborate through digital technologies, participate in society through public and private digital services, manage one’s own digital identity and reputation;
- Area 3. Digital **content creation**: people are able to create and edit digital content, improve and integrate information and content into existing body of knowledge, understanding how copyright and licences are to be applied;
- Area 4. **Safety**: people can protect devices, content, personal data and privacy, as well as their physical and psychological health, and are aware of digital technologies for social well-being and social inclusion¹⁶;
- Area 5. **Problem solving**: people can and resolve identify needs and problems in digital environments, keep up-to-date with the digital evolution.

In our scale we make reference to proficiency levels to map onto different vitality levels. Because we want to model the propaedeutical nature of this dimension for the use of languages digitally, we do not need complex/articulated levels and therefore will use four proficiency levels as identified by Eurostat on

¹²<https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/digcomp>

¹³<https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/desi>

¹⁴see the Digital Agenda key indicators - Digital Skills

¹⁵see the ‘Individuals’ level of digital skills’ dataset

¹⁶safety, however, is not taken into account in the Eurostat survey, nor in the DESI

the basis of DigComp1.0 [12]. At least up to 2017, Eurostat, in fact, calculates overall digital competences and skills of individuals according to four proficiency levels according to the following criteria (see [1] and for details¹⁷):

no skills : no competences at all

low : some competences are present, but at least one area is not covered at all

basic : at least one competence per area is achieved

above basic : more than one competence for all areas are present

Table 3 shows our proposal for a mapping of digital skills and proficiency onto the vitality levels defined in section 2.

Label	Score	Micro Indicators
low	1	individuals have no or low e-skills
basic+	2	individuals have basic or above basic e-skills

Table 3: Digital Literacy Proficiency

Another factor that might be relevant especially for the assessment of the vitality of minority, endangered languages, is age. In fact, older generations tend to be less digitally literate and at the same time (orally) more active and proficient in many if not most endangered languages. However, it is hard to define one and the same age group valid for all regions and languages, and the situation is very likely to change considerably in the near future as digital literacy is increasing rapidly (at least in Europe). Thus, age groups will not be taken into account in the present document.

How to assess digital literacy. Ideally, we would need reliable data on the e-skills of actual speakers of the language under assessment. In practice, this is seldom available as the language dimension is not (yet) taken into account in official national surveys, and thus need to be approximated by using statistics at regional or country level. Thus, when applying the scale to assess the vitality of RMLs using such sources, we must be aware that the outcome is likely to overestimate the situation.

The EC has made the improvement of digital literacy and competence of EU citizens one of the key strategic elements of its Digital Agenda and runs yearly surveys to assess ‘Individuals’ level of computer skills’ and makes the data publicly on a regular basis¹⁸.

¹⁷See also <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/news/new-comprehensive-digital-skills-indicator>

¹⁸Check [Seehttps://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/new-comprehensive-digital-skills-indicator](https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/new-comprehensive-digital-skills-indicator)

Label	Score	Micro Indicators
scarce	1	no regular internet use (< once a week)
good	2	regular internet use (> once a week)

Table 4: Internet penetration level

The reference value for setting the discriminating threshold, could be established similarly to the connectivity dimension: in the case of EU languages we might take the minimum figure reported by Eurostat among: UK, Spain, Portugal, France and Germany (e.g. 50% for 2017). Practically, this would mean to assign score 1 if < 50% of the population has no or low overall digital skills, score 2 otherwise.

4.1.3 Internet penetration or digital population size

Internet penetration is defined as the percentage of Internet users over the total population, and is usually estimated by the number of persons who accessed the Internet in a period that usually goes from 3 to 12 months maximum from any device, including mobile phones¹⁹. In recent surveys and studies it includes also estimates of the frequency of use; Eurostat, for instance, considers regular internet users people who accessed the Internet at least once a week within the reference period²⁰. The EC includes ‘Internet usage’ in the annual calculation of the DESI, and starting from 2018 it is a sub-dimension under Digital Skills²¹.

In our attempt to assess the overall ‘digital potential’ of a language, Internet penetration is considered as a basic precondition for any sign of language digital vitality. Therefore, we include an estimate of the digital population size, in terms of the proportion of regular Internet users over the total population of a given language community, independently of the specific language used on the Internet. The rationale behind this is that if, irrespective of the actual language of use, there is a high number of speakers of the language that use the Internet regularly, then the potential for that language to be used is higher than if the overall use of the Internet was less diffuse or less frequent among its speakers. For instance, if most speakers of, say, Sardinian used the Internet regularly, albeit mostly in Italian, then the potential for Sardinian to be used on the Internet would be higher than if they used the Internet rarely overall.

The table 4 reports the assessment mapping for this indicator.

¹⁹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_countries_by_number_of_Internet_users
and

²⁰https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Internet_use

²¹DESI 2018 Methodological Note: http://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=52297

How to measure Internet penetration Similarly to the other two indicators above, at present the data available does not allow us to distinguish language groups among Internet users, and therefore we can only rely on global statistics that can be taken as rough approximation of the estimates needed. Internet World Stats²² and ITU²³ provide worldwide, country level statistics, while Eurostat also offers NUTS2 breakdowns for Internet use ²⁴.

If we adopt the same strategy defined for the previous indicators, in the case of EU languages we would set the threshold at the minimum value of % of individuals using the Internet regularly, e.g. 71% (Eurostat, 2017).

4.1.4 Character encoding and input/output methods

With over 1 billion people with mobile phones, the 15% Internet penetration rate will soon grow. This in turn will help a lot many Indians to get access to the Internet. If these people are not educated about native language input then they will be unnecessarily constricted by the English-centric Internet.

Subhashish Panigrahi^a

^aSubhashish Panigrahi, 8 Challenges In Growing Indian-Language Wikipedias

Unavailability of character/script encoding (e.g. Unicode) severely limits the digital usability of a language, although it does not completely forbid it. In fact, Cunliffe (2007) ([8, 137]) reports about cases of users adapting the representation of their language to suit the available technology, instead than waiting for a technology to become available, for instance in the case of Romanisation of Egyptian Arabic and Greek. In theory, a language can nevertheless be digitally present in its oral form, e.g. through video or audio. However, since the Internet is still predominantly a written medium, the possibility for a written digital use represents a clear indicator of digital usability. Having its script included in the universal character set is crucial for a language to participate in the technological advancements of computing, as well as to promote native language education, literacy, and cultural preservation. Moreover, character encoding based on internationally accepted standards enables worldwide interchange of

²²<http://www.internetworldstats.com>

²³<https://www.itu.int>,

https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-D/Statistics/Documents/statistics/2016/Individuals_Internet_2000-2015.xls

²⁴http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Digital_economy_and_digital_society_statistics_at_regional_level

Label	Score	Micro Indicators
unsupported	1	language with no standardised script encoding and no alternative script is used
informal	2	language with no standardised script encoding; alternative supported script is used
developing	3	language for which a script proposal is available
proposed	4	language with a consistent and agreed upon encoding that may not have entered already the standardisation process
standardised	5	language with a standardised character/script encoding; fonts, keyboards and software may not be fully available
supported	6	language with a standardised character/script encoding; fonts, keyboards and software is updated and available

Table 5: Input and output methods

text in electronic form.²⁵

There are many different types of character encodings at present, but the ones we deal most frequently with are ASCII, 8-bit encodings, and Unicode-based encodings. Most language scripts and alphabets are represented by Unicode standard,²⁶ but nevertheless there is still evidence of spoken languages for which this is not available.

This indicator also takes into account the availability of input methods such as a specific keyboard, when needed. Instead, it does not consider whether the language has a standardised writing system, which of course plays a role on overall digital usability and use, as this is considered to have an indirect influence on the indicators pertaining to the digital usability and performance measured elsewhere in the scale. Here we are interested in the technological preconditions for using a language on digital devices, irrespective of standardisation.

How to measure character encoding and input/output methods For a list of Unicode supported scripts see the “Supported Scripts” Unicode page (<http://www.unicode.org/standard/supported.html>); other sources are the Unicode consortium (<http://www.unicode.org/versions/Unicode9.0.0/>), the

²⁵Inability to represent non-Latin characters is a legacy of the English and Western based development of the Internet. Over the years, modern standards have come to make it possible to represent a wide range of characters. It must be borne in mind, however, that these standards are supported by software packages and versions of them with great variability, and that often, minority language communities have access to older technology with limited ability to represent the characters they need [8, 137]

²⁶<https://www.unicode.org/standard/standard.html>

Script Encoding Initiative (<http://linguistics.berkeley.edu/sei/index.html>), and the Wikipedia page about Unicode font (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Unicode_font)

4.1.5 Availability of language resources

The availability of language resources (electronic dictionaries, corpora, grammars, etc.) is an essential condition for allowing the development of natural language processing applications, from basic ones such as spell-checkers, to advanced ones such as machine translation applications. Texting and messaging, for instance, is crucially enabled not only by the availability of keyboard characters, but also by the integration of auto-correction devices.

By using the term *availability*, we refer to the fact that a particular language resource or tool can be used by a technology that enables the speakers to carry out a task or receive a service. The mere existence of a resource that is not exploited to provide services or is in an experimental or prototype phase does not satisfy the requirement of availability. For instance, the fact that a prototype spell checker exists for a language, but is not embedded by any application, makes it not available to the community.

For the purpose of assessing the digital capacity of a language, we distinguish the following types of language resources (LRs):

- Basic: monolingual and bilingual e-dictionaries; digital corpus (<100 million words); Part-of-Speech tagging, spell-checker
- Intermediate: corpus driven monolingual dictionary; digital corpus (>100 million words); parallel corpora; web-corpora; term extraction software; shallow syntactic parsing; basic machine translation (rule-based); speech synthesis (TTS)
- Advanced: large corpora (Gw), multilingual corpora; deep syntactic parsing; WordNet, semantic processing; advanced machine translation (statistical (SMT), hybrid, neural); speech recognition.²⁷

Using those levels of LR as a reference, we propose the following scale:

Measuring the availability of digital language resources We are aware that knowledge about language resources in the sense used here very much belongs to a specialistic domain and is a kind of information not readily available to non-experts. Moreover, instruments for assessing the availability of language resources for the various languages are still under development. Possible

²⁷MT: the rationale to differentiate basic MT and advanced MT, and to define them respectively as rule-based and SMT/hybrid/neural, is that minority languages usually cannot benefit from SMT when their technological development is taking its first steps and the sociolinguistic situation is precarious, because of data scarceness (lack of parallel corpora, or comparable corpora useful for SMT). Thus, the first attempts usually intend to develop RBMT systems.

Label	Score	Micro Indicators
none	1	no language resources available in digital format
minimal	2	e-dictionary (bilingual or monolingual)
limited	3	at least two basic LRs
medium	4	basic LRs and, at least, three intermediate LRs
strong	5	most of the intermediate LRs
high	6	most of the advanced LRs

Table 6: Language resources

sources of information are the LREMap ([4], [25]), the CLARIN Virtual Language Observatory,²⁸ the catalogues of Linguistic Data Consortium,²⁹ ELRA³⁰ and META-SHARE.³¹ By filtering the search with the name or ISO code of a specific language, these sites will return the language resources that are registered on these sites. Other useful reference work is the META-NET Language White Papers series [24], where the technological support for natural language processing applications is assessed for 31 EU languages, including some regional languages (Basque, Catalan, Galician and Welsh). An extension of this approach to all EU regional and minority languages would be desirable.

4.2 Digital presence and use

Once the infrastructural level of digital capacity is secured, it becomes possible for a language to be used on a variety of different media and for a varied range of different purposes. The second group of indicators (from 6 to 9) refers to how and how much a language is digitally used: whether and the extent to which it is used for communicating, for creative content production, or for *edutainment* purposes, among the many other possible. The common denominator to this group of indicators is the fact of referring to the creation of digital content in the language, whether it is used for communicating or for other purposes. Again, the indicators are ordered so as to suggest a certain progression upwards: texting, messaging, and e-mailing are seen as more basic functions than, for instance, writing Wikipedia articles or developing e-books or videogames in the language. The communicative function is considered as more basic than other ones, following Gibson [15]. These digital uses of the language also encompass a progression from more private uses of the language to more public (and often official) ones. We have highlighted four indicators for this class: *Use for e-communication*, *Use on social media*, *Availability of Internet media*, and *Wikipedia*.

²⁸<https://vlo.clarin.eu>

²⁹<https://www ldc.upenn.edu/>

³⁰<http://catalog.elra.info/>

³¹<http://www.meta-share.eu/>

Label	Score	Micro Indicators
none	2	no use for e-communication
minimal	3	at least one communication medium that is used at least rarely
medium	4	at least two communication media that are used at least occasionally
strong	5	> two communication media that are used at least regularly
high	6	more than two communication media that are used everyday

Table 7: Use for e-communication

4.2.1 Use for e-communication

This indicator aims at capturing whether the language is being used digitally for interpersonal communication among people. E-communication, especially under the form of instant messaging, shares many features with orality, and as such is one of the privileged contexts where spontaneous forms of expressions emerge. The one-to-one directionality of messages adds a privacy dimension, which fosters incipient uses of a language, often by users not fully confident with its written standard. While the tendency is to think of media such as e-mail, texting or other forms of instant messaging for e-communication, we should not forget audio-only channels such as Skype. From the perspective of using e-communication as an indicator of digital language vitality, it is important to capture not only the variety and quantity of media available, but also the frequency with which they are used. Therefore, the different values for this indicator are expressed under the form of “rules” for assigning a particular value on the basis of the occurrence of particular frequency conditions.

We propose the following scale:

How to assess e-communication. Because this indicator mainly refers to private communication exchanges, at present there is no objective or reliable source of information that can be used to estimate its value, and it is quite unlikely that there will be one in the future, for privacy matters. At present the main source of information for this indicator is therefore a survey of the type carried out in the DLDP project.³² If information is to be collected through a survey, then we suggest to apply a threshold of at least 60% of respondents to ensure reliability of the information provided.

³²<http://www.dldp.eu/content/reports-digital-language-diversity-europe>

Label	Score	Micro Indicators
none	2	no use on social media
minimal	3	one or two social media that are used at least rarely
medium	4	at least three social media that are used at least regularly
strong	5	at least three social media, one of which is used at least everyday
high	6	more than three social media used everyday or at least regularly

Table 8: Use on social media

4.2.2 Use on social media

Recently, a body of research has investigated the role played by social networks in minority language use, Facebook [9] and Twitter [19] in particular [16]. While debate is still ongoing as whether new media have a positive or a negative influence on minority language use, it is plain that use on social media, such as blogs, Twitter and Facebook is a strong indicator of active digital use of a language. Social networking sites are “more orientated to participatory interpersonal and inter-social communication” and have been linked to the development of literature outside formal and official contexts. Social media do not merely function as means for computer-mediated communication. On top of that, they act as virtual spaces of expression: they transform language speakers from consumers to creators of content, and especially in local contexts, they represent “important new domains with the potential to impact upon the use of a minority language” [19]. As such, they are a crucial indicator of digital vitality of a language.

Similarly to what suggested for the previous indicator about e-communication (4.2.1), we consider the variety of social media where the language is used and the frequency of use as the main criteria for estimating the use of a language on social media. We do not take into account the distinction between active and passive use. Although passive use cannot be discarded as a sign of vitality, active use is a more appropriate indication of digital vitality in this particular context.

We propose the following scale:

How to assess use on social media Ideally, this indicator should assess the amount of social media content being shared in a given language. At the time of writing, however, we are not aware of tools or applications being able to crawl social media on the basis of a specific language requirement, either because not all networks allow to crawl their data (as is the case for Facebook) or because language identification is a technology still under development for the vast majority of languages. A few exceptions about which we are aware are

for Twitter, the Indigenous Tweets service³³, that allows to derive the amount of Twitter accounts and tweets in a number of languages. For Basque one might also use UMAP³⁴ or Talaia³⁵. Software as such would allow to assess the amount of content available in a language for the various social media. Until this ideal condition is met, we suggest to resort once again to the information that can be gathered through an informative questionnaire of the type developed for the DLDAP project. If based on a questionnaire, we suggest to apply a threshold of at least 60% to ensure reliability.

4.2.3 Availability of Internet media

With this indicator we aim to capture the variety of Internet media that are available in a given language, with a sufficient amount of content. The term “Internet media” broadly refers to a range of communicative instruments such as web pages and websites, blogs, forums, but also Internet radio and TV, allowing production and consumption of content in digital form. A typical Internet medium is represented by Wikipedia, but in the context of the Digital Language Vitality Scale we will treat it separately, for reasons that will be made clear below. Internet media are in most cases traditional media delivered for consumption on a new platform (e.g. television or radio programmes delivered online, e-books); others are radically new forms of content production and consumption, and include a dimension of interactivity that was not possible in the preceding era, where content was published in print and reactions to it would take the form of edited letters. Because of the relative ease and affordability of their creation and use, Internet media provide a viable alternative for content creation in minority languages that are often deprived of the institutional support that would be essential for traditional media such as . And because of the centrality of digital media in modern life, their availability in a language is as well a sign of the (digital) vitality of that language, its use conquering new and important contexts. The existence of many different types of available media, such as websites, audio or video streaming, archives or e-books is thus taken as a proxy of vitality. These are the proposed scores:

At the time of writing, we have identified a list of relevant types of Internet media:³⁶

- websites (includes publicly available websites, and private such as intranets and extranets)
- smartphone apps

³³<http://indigenoustweets.com>

³⁴<https://www.codesyntax.com/en/blog/basque-trends-content-and-user-rankings-in-twitter-umap>

³⁵<http://talaia.elhuyar.eus/indexES.html/>. Talaia can be downloaded from GitHub: <https://github.com/elhuyar/BehaguneUI>

³⁶The same list was also used in the DLDAP survey (<http://www.dldap.eu/content/reports-digital-language-diversity-europe>)

Label	Score	Micro Indicators
none	2	no Internet media available in the language
limited	3	some Internet media available in the language (= 1 to 2)
medium	4	some Internet media available in the language (= 3 to 4)
strong	5	a considerable variety of Internet media is available (= 5 to 6)
advanced	6	a wide variety of Internet media is available (≥ 6)

Table 9: Availability of Internet media

- Internet television (both television channels delivered by the Internet, such as Netflix service, or individual TV shows offered via the websites of channels)
- blogs and Forums/message boards
- streaming audio (including podcasts and Internet radio)
- streaming video (including webcasts, podcasts, YouTube and Vimeo videos/channels)
- eBooks
- digital libraries and archives

How to assess the availability of Internet media The ideal source of information would be a dedicated survey or official surveys/censuses, if available. If a survey is exploited, we suggest to apply a threshold in order to enhance reliability. For instance, $>$ or $=$ to 30% of respondents.

4.2.4 Wikipedia

“Wikipedia widens the topics and the domains in which dialects are used online” [23], thus contributing to their overall vitality. According to Kornai [21], Wikipedia plays a central role in determining the extent to which a language is digitally ascending: “There may be small bulletin boards, mailing lists, Yahoo, or Google groups scattered around, but experience shows that Wikipedia is always among the very first active digital language communities, and can be safely used as an early indicator of some language actually crossing the digital divide.” ([20]:3).

An interesting remark made by Miola ([23]) concerns the particular variety used for regional/minority Wikipedias. He notes how, for instance, the variety used for the Wikipedia in Piedmontese does not reflect any of the varieties actually spoken, thus suggesting a role for this Wikipedia on the symbolic/ideological

side rather than on the *real* one. Similarly, Wikipedias can function as *Ausbauisat*ion factories: virtual places where a common language is created and reinforced to be used in high, cultivated language domains. This particular role of Wikipedia as a sign not only of digital use, but also of active interest in the creation of digital content stands behind the decision of considering Wikipedia as a separate indicator of digital vitality.

The sheer existence of a Wikipedia should not be overestimated as a healthy sign of digital vitality, though: not only are there Wikipedias for classical languages (this is the case of *Vicipaedia*, the Wikipedia in Latin language³⁷), but it can also happen that a Wikipedia project is set up by a small number of activists with no correspondence with frequent and active digital uses of the language outside the Wikipedia community.

The most straightforward and easily accessible sign of the weight of a Wikipedia as an indicator of language vitality is its number of articles. This data is provided by the Wikipedia Foundation at the page “List of Wikipedias”³⁸. For a more precise characterization of the size of a Wikipedia, we should consider other indicators as well, such as the amount of total words. However, this data is not directly accessible: Wikimedia Foundation offers the possibility to download data dumps³⁹ and there are several tools to extract the text content⁴⁰.

Other sub-indicators that have been proposed estimate the activity over a given Wikipedia, in terms of total number of users involved, and the ratio of active users (i.e. users who performed at least one action on a Wikipedia) over total users (i.e. users who performed at least one action in a period of 30 days) cf.[23]. Page view statistics could also be relevant because they measure how much a Wikipedia in a minority language is used. Finally, Wikipedia includes a measure of the “Depth”, i.e. a “rough indicator of a Wikipedia’s quality, showing how frequently its articles are updated.”⁴¹

Therefore, even if other sub-indicators could, in principle, give a more precise measure of the vitality of a Wikipedia, the number of articles is easily obtainable and fully reliable, and cannot be considered as an insignificant index [18]⁴². Wikipedia in MLs are artifacts with a symbolic value and the number of articles increases their visibility. The number of contributors is not visible just reading pages and it has no impact on the opinion of the reader about the use of a minority language on the Internet.

The table below illustrates a grading according to number of Wikipedia articles only. The intervals in the number of articles are those used by Wikipedia to classify the different language editions⁴³.

³⁷https://la.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vicipaedia:Pagina_prima

³⁸https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/List_of_Wikipedias

³⁹<https://dumps.wikimedia.org/>

⁴⁰wikiextractor, wikipedia2text, Pandoc

⁴¹https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia_article_depth

⁴²It is also to be considered whether it can be useful to add the ratio of articles per 100 actual speakers. This, however, will bring the drawback of having to rely on data that are at best not entirely reliable, if not missing altogether.

⁴³<https://www.wikipedia.org/>

Label	Score	Micro Indicators
none	1	no Wikipedia
incubator	2	a small Wikipedia is available (less than 100 articles)
small	3	between 100 and 10,000 articles
medium	4	between 10,000 and 100,000 articles
large	5	between 100,000 and 1,000,000 articles
huge	6	over 1,000,000 articles

Table 10: Wikipedia

4.3 Digital Performance

The category of *Digital performance* groups together indicators referring to what can be digitally done with a language. In some way, this is a different take at the extent to which a language is used over different media: the perspective here is more on the purposes for which it is used rather than on the range of available media where it is used. We have identified five indicators for this group: *Availability of Internet services*, *Localised social network*, *Localised software*, *Machine translation tools/services*, and *Dedicated Internet top-level domain*.

4.3.1 Availability of Internet services

This indicator refers to the presence of digital services localised in the language (e.g. online news, search engines, e-commerce sites, etc.). Here is the list of types of Internet services that was used in the DLDP survey and which are up-to-date relevant services at the time of writing:

- online newspapers
- online news
- search engines (e.g. Google)
- edu-tainment products and services, (e.g. videogames, children-friendly websites, digital apps)
- entertainment (music channel, movies, etc.)
- video subtitling
- health services
- e-Commerce services (e.g. airline reservation sites, local e-shopping services)
- public Administration/eGovernment (e.g. local county)

Label	Score	Micro Indicators
none	2	No digital services available in the language (= less than 1)
limited	3	Some digital services available in the language (= 1 to 2)
medium	4	Some digital services available in the language (= 3 to 5)
strong	5	a considerable variety of digital services is available (= 6 to 8)
advanced	6	a wide variety of digital services is available (≥ 8)

Table 11: Availability of Internet services

- eBanking (online banking services offered by bank)
- cultural services (e.g. virtual museums and heritage websites)
- tourist information and services (e.g. tourist agencies)
- advertising, promotion and marketing
- customer care

The table below gives the scoring indications.

How to assess availability of Internet services. Ideally, objective data (e.g. registries or catalogues) would be needed about the number of different services existing for the language under assessment. However, such data is currently often non-existent. Alternatively, one can rely on own independent research of the available services, either relying on one’s own knowledge of the local language community and situation, and/or on data collected through a survey like the one carried out in the DLDP project. When using survey data, we suggest to apply a threshold greater than or equal to 40% of respondents to enhance reliability.

4.3.2 Localised social networks

This indicator refers to the presence of social media with a localised interface. The most popular social networks offer their interface localised in a number of different languages: at the time of writing, Facebook offers 113 languages, Twitter 48. It is still debated whether the availability of interfaces translated or localised has any positive influence on the use of a language instead of another. In a study of the use of Puerto Rican Spanish on MySpace, Carroll [6] argued that an English-language interface lead to the adoption of English terminology, and this would encourage to think that the availability of a translated

Label	Score	Micro Indicators
none	3	No social media localised in the language
limited	4	At least one social media interfaces localised in the language (= 1)
medium	5	Some social media interfaces localised in the language (= 2 to 3)
advanced	6	Many social media interfaces localised in the language (= > 3)

Table 12: Localised social networks

interface would promote the use of the same language. Unfortunately, there are no studies available inquiring this correlation. Cunliffe’s research ([9]) revealed little evidence that the Facebook Welsh interface was a positive influence to use Welsh. In any case, we share Cunliffe’s view that that the mere existence of a localised interface has a positive influence on the perception of the language as modern and suited to being used in ICT contexts.

How to measure localised social networks Checking whether a social network is available in a language is fairly simple. For Facebook, you’ll have to select ”Language” from the menu ”Settings”, and then search for a particular language on the list that appears when clicking on the question “Which language do you want to use Facebook in?”. On Twitter, the available languages appear immediately from the “Account” menu. For social networks that are less widely available, a survey might serve as a reliable source of information.

4.3.3 Localised software: operating systems and basic software

This indicator focuses on the availability of localised software. Computer software is usually classified into three categories⁴⁴: 1) system software or operating systems; 2) application software, that can be general purpose (word processing, web browsers, etc.) or special purpose software (accounting, database systems, audio and video production, etc.); and 3) computer programming tools. The last category has not been considered as an indicator of vitality, since hardly any of those types of tools are localised. Localisation of software is carried out in different ways. Sometimes, localisation can be done by the system developers themselves, but, in the case of regional/minority languages, it is usually promoted or even undertaken by users’ communities, local stakeholders or institutions, who want to use the afore-mentioned software in their own language. At this point, it is important to mention that, in some cases, localised software does exist in the RML language, but for many reasons, the user’s community

⁴⁴https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Software_categories

Label	Score	Micro Indicators
none	2	Neither operating system nor general purpose software localised in the language
limited	3	At least one operating system (either desktop or mobile, either open or commercial) localised in the language
medium	4	At least one desktop and one mobile operating system (either open or commercial) + some general purpose software (a word processor and a browser) localised in the language
strong	5	Most used operating systems and general purpose software localised in the language; some specific purpose application software localised.
advanced	6	Main operating systems and application software localised in the language.

Table 13: Localised software

does not know about it, and therefore, does not use it. Also, in ML situations, where computers may be shared within bilingual families/organisations, the default is usually the majority language as changing languages, especially at the level of operating systems, is clunky and time-consuming.

How to check for localised software In order to give a value to this indicator, one can rely on personal experience with the software and operating systems used. If an assessment of a language different than the one spoken is made (which is not recommended), then the following sources of information can be useful. The notion of what counts as “main” software and operating systems is clearly variable and cultural-dependent. In the context of the DLDP survey we used a list of software and operating systems and asked people to reply whether they knew if a localised version was available. We report the list here to help the interested reader: Windows, Mac OS X, GNU/Linux, Android, iOS, Microsoft Office, LibreOffice/OpenOffice, Firefox, Chrome, Internet Explorer, Thunderbird, Adobe Creative Suite, Gimp. This list may need to be modified as needed. If using a questionnaire to elicit this information, we recommend to check afterwards, because we have observed a tendency from respondents to overestimate the availability of localised interfaces.

4.3.4 Machine translation tools/services

This is an indicator of the “proficiency” level of language use on digital media and the availability of machine translation services and tools is considered from the user’s perspective, rather than from the point of view of the availability of

Label	Score	Micro Indicators
none	3	No MT for the language
basic	4	at least one (online) service/ tool, at least one language pair or one direction
medium	5	at least one (online) service / tool, at least two language pairs in both directions
advanced	6	more than one (online) service /tool, more than 5 language pairs

Table 14: Machine translation tools/services

the technology *per se*. So this indicator about MT counts differently as in the "Digital capacity" section. Since machine translation technology presupposes a wide array of tools and resources, last but not least the availability of big multilingual corpora, this indicator can be taken as a benchmark of strong and active digital use. Moreover, from the point of view of the digital usability of the language, the availability of reliable MT for a language is a sign that the language has gained a fairly high level of digital presence and importance. The availability of Machine Translation contributes to the "de-minorization" of minor languages ([14, 2]), and contributes heavily to improving their status, by increasing normality, literacy, and visibility.⁴⁵ In the context of the Digital Language Vitality Scale, the availability of MT is an indicator of increasing vitality, use, and prestige. Here we are ignoring the technical complexity of the realization of MT tools, and focus instead on whether there are usable tools for automatic translations (either online or as standalone tools). Therefore, we consider as good indicators the number of different services/tools, the number of language pairs and possibly the directions (e.g. whether from language1 to language2 or the reverse as well).

How to check for (availability) of MT services. Checking if Google provides MT services for a language, is fairly easy: the Google Translate page offers a list of available languages.⁴⁶ Another important source of reference for open-source machine translation is the Apertium page (<https://www.apertium.org>), as well as the list of tools available on this page.⁴⁷

Probably, it is quite safe to rely (even if not exclusively) on the knowledge of the respondents to a questionnaire, since whether a service/tool is known and used by the digital users of the language should have some relevance, and would also be a way to account for the spread of the service within the community.

⁴⁵Forcada [14] also argues that the use of MT systems may contribute to the standardisation of a language by promoting a writing or spelling system.

⁴⁶<https://translate.google.com/intl/en/about/languages/>

⁴⁷<http://fosmt.org>

Label	Score	Micro Indicators
No	3	No dedicated Internet top-level domain
Yes	5	There is a dedicated Internet top-level domain

Table 15: Dedicated Internet top-level domain

4.3.5 Dedicated Internet top-level domain

This indicator is related to the existence of a top-level domain name (a geographic top-level domain or GeoTLD) dedicated to a certain linguistic and cultural community (e.g. .cat; .eus; .bzh). A GeoTLD is a generic top-level domain using the name of or invoking an association with a geographical, geopolitical, ethnic, linguistic or cultural community.⁴⁸ The success of the .cat top-level domain name inspired the creation of independent Internet identities for linguistic and cultural communities.

The fact that a language has its own top-level domain name cannot be unequivocally interpreted as a sign of high vitality. The precise vitality level depends also on the penetration of the domain in the geographical area where the regional/minority language is used, and on the proportion of websites within the domain that are written in the regional/minority language.⁴⁹ Moreover, as pointed out by Cunliffe (2007) [8], it is unlikely that small minority language communities will meet ICANN’s (the Internet Corporation for Assigned Names and Numbers) criteria. On the other hand, neither is the existence of a dedicated domain name a necessary condition for vitality, because, in principle, a language can be digitally thriving without a dedicated domain name.

Nevertheless, languages having their own top-level domain name present a non-negligible digital activity, indicating that there is some level of correlation between the existence of the domain and digital vitality. Moreover, a dedicated domain name can be taken also as an indicator of a strong digital identity. The values proposed for this indicator are yes / no and if no, the minimum corresponding level could be ‘emergent’ (thus score 3) while in case of presence of an Internet domain the minimum level would be ‘vital’ (thus 5).

How to check for the existence of a dedicated Internet top-level domain. Information about current top-level domains (TLDs) is provided by the ICANN website⁵⁰. A database of TLDs is maintained at IANA (<http://www.iana.org/domains/root/db>). For identifying the linking of a domain to a language and culture this Wikipedia list can be more useful ([⁴⁸\[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Generic_top-level_domain#Geographic_gTLD\]\(https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Generic_top-level_domain#Geographic_gTLD\)](https://en.</p>
</div>
<div data-bbox=)

⁴⁹<https://www.domeinuak.eus/wp-content/uploads/2015/12/PuntuEUS-Observatory-2015.pdf>

⁵⁰<https://www.icann.org/resources/pages/registries/registries-en>

wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_Internet_top-level_domains#Geographic_top-level_domains)⁵¹.

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⁵¹We still need to verify whether there is public information on requested domains, not yet granted. This might lead to a revision of the grades (No, Requested, Yes) and in a different scoring.

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